

Method of burnup calculation of spent fuel assemblies of the IVV-2M research reactor using the MCU-PTR software tool

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Abstract

Research reactors (RRs) are widely used for research in fundamental physics, materials science, and for radioisotope production. One of the problems in the field of mathematical modeling of research reactors is the verification of computational codes used for the calculation of neutron-physical parameters. To pass the verification procedure, it is necessary to justify the methods of mathematical modeling and the accuracy of the RR geometric model. Currently, precision programs allow creating a RR geometric model of any degree of detail. However, the degree of this detail has not been formulated. The paper considers the justification of the parameters of spatio-temporal discretization of IVV-2M-type fuel assemblies when calculating the burnup distribution. Determining the frequency of dividing the fuel assembly model into layers by the height of its active part significantly affects such parameters as the effective neutron multiplication factor (K_{eff}), energy release at the maximum stress point. Moreover, the degree of detail and the set of calculation statistics affect the calculation duration, which can be reduced by applying a certain approach to modeling. It should also be noted that the issue of the need for a fuel pin (or more detailed, in the horizontal plane) degree of burnup calculation was not considered due to the lack of control over the orientation of the IVV-2M fuel assemblies in the horizontal plane during the operation of the IVV-2M research reactor.

Keywords

MCU-PTR, research reactor (RR), fuel assembly (FA), degree of burnup, calculation, effective neutron multiplication factor (K_{eff})

Introduction

The first physical start-up of the IVV-2 reactor was carried out in April 1966. In order to increase the experimental capabilities of the reactor, the reactor was modernized in 1970–76, after which it received a new name, IVV-2M. As a result of the modernization, almost all reactor systems were

replaced, as a result of which the nominal value of the reactor's thermal power was increased from 10 to 15 MW (Russkikh 2017; Tashlykov et al. 2023; Van Thuong et al. 2023).

The initial data for justifying the parameters of the spatio-temporal discretization of the calculation models of the IVV-2M fuel assemblies were the starting load of the IVV-2M RR (1976), as well as the operational

configurations of the IVV-2M RR core, operated in 2017 after the next comprehensive technical maintenance of the RR lasting more than 8 days.

The initial data for modeling the IVV-2M RR specifies the material composition and geometry of the elements used in the problem. Models of the operational sections of the core elements are built in accordance with the design documentation for the IVV-2M RR. The configuration of the end parts is simplified compared to the real object and does not have a significant impact on the reliability of the calculations.

The paper presents data on the justification of:

- Assignment of the initial average fuel degree of burnup for the IVV-2M fuel assembly;
- Selection of the optimal spatial division when calculating the distribution of fuel degree of burnup in the IVV-2M fuel assembly;
- Selection of the time step when calculating fuel degree of burnup in the IVV-2M fuel assembly.
- Recommendations are given for conducting further calculations of the radionuclide composition of fuel, and their implementation is shown in several campaigns of the RR operation.

MCU-PTR software tool

The MCU-PTR software tool (Alexeyev et al. 2010; Alexeyev et al. 2011) is designed to simulate the processes of neutron, photon, electron, and positron transfer by the Monte Carlo method based on the evaluated nuclear data in systems with three-dimensional geometry, taking into account the change in the nuclide composition of materials during interaction with neutrons. For all the above particles, a non-homogeneous equation of particle transfer is solved, and for neutrons, the program allows solving a homogeneous equation. Mathematically, this means that for the system under consideration, a kinetic equation with specified boundary conditions is solved, describing the distribution of the particle flux in it. In this case, the effective neutron multiplication factor, the distribution of energy release by fuel assemblies and individual fuel elements, the effective fraction of delayed neutrons, particle fluxes, and other functionals are recorded.

MCU-PTR can operate in two modes – static and dynamic. In the static mode, the reactor characteristics are calculated for a given nuclide composition of its materials. In the dynamic mode, the change in the nuclide composition is taken into account, and the same characteristics are calculated depending on the reactor operating time. To calculate the change in the nuclide composition of the reactor materials, the BURNUP module is used, which implements an iterative calculation scheme (predictor-corrector) to take into account the dependence of cross-sections on time. This allows using relatively large step sizes and thereby reducing the overall program execution time. All the characteristics of burnable nuclei required for the calculation are

collected in the BURN library, which contains data for approximately 1,100 nuclides.

There are other software tools for calculating the neutron physics characteristics of reactor cores, such as MCNP-5 and ORIGEN. However, according to the legislation of the Russian Federation, in order to build computational models of processes affecting the safety of nuclear energy facilities, it is required to use programs for electronic computers that have been reviewed by the scientific and technical support organization of the authorized state safety regulatory authority. The MCU-PTR software tool applied to process modelling in the IVV-2M research nuclear reactor, as well as MCU-RFFI/A, has passed an examination in the specified organization and has a certification passport.

Geometric model of the IVV-2M RR core and reflector

A brief description and the main characteristics of the IVV-2M RR are given in (Russkikh 2017; Tashlykov et al. 2017; Zyryanova et al. 2018; Tashlykov et al. 2023; Van Thuong et al. 2023).

The geometric model of the IVV-2M RR core is constructed in accordance with the design documentation. The horizontal experimental channels, graphite reflector, concrete massif, support grid, and stainless steel reactor pool lining have a simplified representation, which does not affect the criticality of the system and the distribution of the neutron flux density in the core (Fig. 1).

The design solutions and block structure of the core and the reflector, the uniformity and interchangeability of the core elements provide the IVV-2M RR with physical and design flexibility, which allows creating various core layouts, changing the number of sections, their dimensions, and placement in the support grid, as well as varying the sizes of experimental devices (EDs) and their neutron-physical and thermal characteristics. Basically, the core is formed by installing hexagonal

Figure 1. Cross-section of the calculation model at the level of the center of the core ($z=25$ cm). 1 – Horizontal experimental channels; 2 – core; 3 – graphite reflector; 4 – reactor pool; 5 – concrete massif.

fuel assemblies (from 36 to 42 pieces) in the support plate, hexagonal beryllium reflector blocks, hexagonal lead and graphite blocks, as well as experimental and irradiation devices. As an example, the loading of the IVV-2M RR No. 1 is shown (Fig. 2). The geometric model of the layout No. 1 of the core of the IVV-2M reactor is shown in Fig. 3.

The geometry and material composition of the core elements are specified according to the design documentation. The calculation model uses the Cartesian coordinate system. The origin of the coordinates is located at the lower boundary of the support grid. The Ox axis is directed along the reactor pool, the Oy axis is across the pool, and the Oz axis is upward.

Figure 2. Cartogram of the IVV-2M RR loading No. 1.

Figure 3. Cross-section of the calculation model at the level of the center of the core ($z=25$ cm).

Geometric model of the IVV-2M fuel assembly

The geometric model of the IVV-2M fuel assembly is shown in Figs 4, 5. Each fuel assembly consists of five tubular hexagonal fuel elements coaxially installed between hexagonal casing tubes; the length from the lower to the upper ends is 870 mm. The structural material of the fuel element assemblies and casings is AMSN-2 aluminum alloy. The fuel layer is uranium dioxide dispersed in an aluminum matrix. Each fuel assembly also has a cavity formed by an internal hexagonal casing tube with an inscribed diameter of 29.1 mm. The operating elements of the reactor control and protection system are installed in these cavities, or various irradiation devices can be installed. The head and the shank of the fuel assembly are specified in a simplified manner. The head of the fuel assembly is represented by a hexagonal prism made of a homogeneous mixture of aluminum and water. The shank is simplified to a hexagonal tube with an external spanner size of 62.8 mm and an internal spanner size of 45.5 mm at the bottom and 29.1 mm at the top. The shank is made of AMSN-2 aluminum alloy. The fuel assembly uses highly enriched uranium-235 fuel.

Figure 4. Diagram of longitudinal and transverse sections of the IVV-2M type fuel assembly. 1 – fuel assembly head; 2 – outer casing tube; 3 – inner casing tube; 4 – fuel element cladding; 5 – fuel core; 6 – fuel assembly shank.

Figure 5. Geometric model of the calculation model of the IVV-2M type fuel assembly. a) longitudinal section; b) cross-section, fuel assembly head $z=74.8\div 79.2$; c) cross-section, fuel elements $z=24.8\div 74.8$; d) cross-section, fuel assembly shank, $z=22.25\div 24.8$; e) cross-section, fuel assembly shank, $z=0.0\div 22.25$.

Degree of burnup is calculated for each fuel assembly separately. At the first stage, there is no division by height or by fuel elements. That is, in the general case, the model specifies from 36 to 42 fuel assembly materials with different degree of burnup. The detail of the spatial division of the model for calculating the burnup distribution in the fuel assembly is determined by its influence on the calculation of such parameters as the neutron multiplication factor and the maximum energy release. To determine the step of a division of the fuel assemblies by degree of burnup, the standard layout No. 1 presented earlier was used.

Justification for setting the initial average degree of burnup for the IVV-2M fuel assembly

To set the initial value of the average degree of burnup for the IVV-2M fuel assemblies, the “Methodology for determining the burnup of uranium-235 and determining the mass of nuclear materials in spent IVV-2M fuel

assemblies” developed at INM JSC was used. According to the method, the change in the concentrations of nuclei

included in this chain of transformations is described by a system of differential equations (1):

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} \frac{dN^{U5}}{dt} &= -R_f^{U5}(N^{U5}) \cdot N^{U5} - R_{n,\gamma}^{U5}(N^{U5}) \cdot N^{U5} \\ \frac{dN^{U8}}{dt} &= -R_f^{U8}(N^{U5}) \cdot N^{U8} - R_{n,\gamma}^{U8}(N^{U5}) \cdot N^{U8} \\ \frac{dN^{Np9}}{dt} &= -R_f^{Np9}(N^{U5}) \cdot N^{Np9} - \lambda_{Np9} \cdot N^{Np9} + R_{n,\gamma}^{U8}(N^{U5}) \cdot N^{U8} \\ \frac{dN^{Pu9}}{dt} &= -R_f^{Pu9}(N^{U5}) \cdot N^{Pu9} + \lambda_{Np9} \cdot N^{Np9} - R_{n,\gamma}^{Pu9}(N^{U5}) \cdot N^{Pu9} \\ \frac{dN^{Pu0}}{dt} &= R_{n,\gamma}^{Pu9}(N^{U5}) \cdot N^{Pu9} - R_f^{Pu0}(N^{U5}) \cdot \varphi \cdot N^{Pu0} - R_{n,\gamma}^{Pu0}(N^{U5}) \cdot N^{Pu0} \\ \frac{dN^{Pu1}}{dt} &= R_{n,\gamma}^{Pu0}(N^{U5}) \cdot N^{Pu0} - R_f^{Pu1}(N^{U5}) \cdot N^{Pu1} - R_{n,\gamma}^{Pu1}(N^{U5}) \cdot N^{Pu1} - \lambda_{Pu1} \cdot N^{Pu1} \end{aligned} \right. \quad (1)$$

Where

$R_f^{U5}(N^{U5}), R_f^{U8}(N^{U5}), R_f^{Np9}(N^{U5}), R_f^{Pu9}(N^{U5}), R_f^{Pu0}(N^{U5}), R_f^{Pu1}(N^{U5})$ – fission reaction rates for $^{235}\text{U}, ^{238}\text{U}, ^{239}\text{Np}, ^{239}\text{Pu}, ^{240}\text{Pu}, ^{241}\text{Pu}$, presented in the form of functional dependencies on the concentration of $^{235}\text{U}, 1/\text{s}$;

$R_{n,\gamma}^{U5}(N^{U5}), R_{n,\gamma}^{U8}(N^{U5}), R_{n,\gamma}^{Pu9}(N^{U5}), R_{n,\gamma}^{Pu0}(N^{U5}), R_{n,\gamma}^{Pu1}(N^{U5})$ – the rates of reactions of radiative neutron capture by nuclei $^{235}\text{U}, ^{238}\text{U}, ^{239}\text{Pu}, ^{240}\text{Pu}, ^{241}\text{Pu}, 1/\text{s}$;

$\lambda_{Np9}, \lambda_{Pu1}$ – decay constants of ^{239}Np and $^{241}\text{Pu}, 1/\text{s}$;

$N^{U5}, N^{U8}, N^{Np9}, N^{Pu9}, N^{Pu0}, N^{Pu1}$ – concentrations of nuclei $^{235}\text{U}, ^{238}\text{U}, ^{239}\text{Np}, ^{239}\text{Pu}, ^{240}\text{Pu}, ^{241}\text{Pu}$ respectively, which are functions of time $t, 1/\text{cm}^3$.

The reaction rates included in the system of differential equations (1) are the total for the entire spectrum and were calculated using the MCU-RFFI/A software tool with certification passport No. 61 dated 17.10.1996. Fig. 6 shows the change in the effective neutron multiplication factor during one reactor operation cycle (campaign), calculated using the MCU-PTR software tool. In this case, the change in the position of the control members and the

nuclide composition in the IVV-2M fuel assemblies were taken into account. For comparison, the effective neutron multiplication factor was calculated for each change in the position of the control members during a campaign (23 steps) and for certain critical positions of the control members (5 steps).

As can be seen from the presented graph, in steady-state reactor operating modes $K_{eff} \sim 1$, which indicates

Figure 6. Change in the effective neutron multiplication factor during one reactor campaign.

the adequacy of the adopted calculation model. Further calculations of the nuclide composition of the IVV-2M fuel assemblies were carried out only using the MCUPTR software.

Selection of the optimal spatial division when calculating the degree of burnup distribution in the IVV-2M fuel assembly

The calculation model of the IVV-2M RR uses a division into one altitude layer by fuel assembly degree of burnup with a thickness occupying the active part of the assembly – 50 cm. The calculations were performed on layout No. 1.

To select the optimal spatial division, two options were considered: in the first, the fuel assembly is divided into 10 equal high layers that burn out as a separate material; in the second – into 5. In this case, to analyze the results, two fuel assemblies were used – K287 (cell 8-7, burnup 32%), which is a “hot” fuel assembly, and K304 (cell 5-6, burnup 0%), as a fuel assembly with a control member. The rod is immersed to a depth of 41 cm from the upper edge of the fuel part of the fuel assembly. During the degree of burnup calculation, the rod was in the same position. The reactor power was 15 MW.

The selected problem gives a conservative estimate of the error of the variant with a less detailed height division in relation to the variant with a more detailed division, since in the problem under consideration the control rod is immersed to a constant depth during the burnout process, whereas in reality it moves.

Table 1 shows the results of calculating the degree of burnup in fuel assemblies during one reactor campaign (20 days on average) at a power of 15 MW with a different number of layers in height.

The difference in the neutron multiplication factor of the variant with 1 altitude layer from the variant with 10 altitude layers is 0.27% $\Delta k/k$ at the time of 10 days and 0.38% $\Delta k/k$ at the time of 20 days. It can also be concluded that the variant with a less detailed altitude division gives almost the same values of uranium-235 degree of burnup as the variant with a more detailed division. The maximum difference in the degree of burnup calculated for 1 altitude layer from the burnup depth obtained by averaging the values calculated for burnup with 10 altitude layers does not exceed 1.3% (relative) for the time of 10 days and 0.08% for the time of 20 days.

Next, to determine the sufficiency of the chosen approach in calculating the average degree of burnup of the fuel assemblies by height, we will consider the degree of burnup of all fuel assemblies during campaigns No. 1÷No. 3. In the first case, at the beginning of campaign No. 1, one fuel assembly is specified by one layer by height; in the second – by five layers by height. The degree of burnup of all fuel assemblies by five layers is distributed according to the relative distribution of K304 fuel assembly at the end of campaign No. 1 (Fig. 7b). The results of calculating the average degree of burnup in fuel assemblies are presented in Table 2.

As can be seen from the presented calculations, the discrepancy in the values of the average degree of burnup for one and five layers is minimal. However, it should be taken into account that the calculation with a constant degree of burnup over the height of the fuel assembly overestimates K_{eff} , since it underestimates the neutron leakage – with a constant degree of burnup over the height, the amount of uranium at the edges of the fuel assembly is less than when divided into several layers by height. To confirm the above, a calculation was performed for campaign No. 1 with the same degree of burnup over the fuel assembly height ($K_{eff} = 0.98132 \pm 0.0002$) and with the degree of burnup distributed over the relative distribution of K304 fuel assembly ($K_{eff} = 0.97320 \pm 0.0002$). The difference in K_{eff} was 0.8% $\Delta K/K$.

Based on the above, further calculations of the degree of burnup must be carried out according to 5 altitude layers.

Selecting a time step when calculating degree of burnup

To select the time step for the IVV-2M reactor model, calculations with different numbers of time steps were performed. Two problems were considered. In the first one, the possibility of calculation without changing the position of the control members was investigated, i.e., their effect on the degree of burnup distribution in the fuel assemblies (arrangement #1, average position of the control members during the campaign and average per day, 500 hours). The second one is a calculation with a time step of 500 hours, i.e., a full campaign, at a power of 15 MW with an unchanged average position of the control members (arrangement #1 all critical states and one large step, average degree of burnup over the fuel assemblies as one volume).

Table 1. The multiplication factor of the core and the average degree of burnup for the fuel assembly, calculated with different numbers of layers by burnup N_z

Time, days	K_{eff}			Burnup of ^{235}U , %					
				K287, cells 8-7			K304, cells 5-6		
	$N_z=1$	$N_z=5$	$N_z=10$	$N_z=1$	$N_z=5$	$N_z=10$	$N_z=1$	$N_z=5$	$N_z=10$
0	0.9976	0.9976	0.9976	31.96	31.96	31.96	0.00	0.00	0.00
10	0.9914	0.9933	0.9887	35.17	35.39	35.17	2.29	2.27	2.26
20	0.9816	0.9832	0.9779	38.32	38.75	38.29	4.46	4.55	4.47

Table 2. Estimated degree of burnup in fuel assemblies (average by volume) at the end of campaigns

№TVS	Campaign #1		Campaign #2		Campaign #3	
	Degree of burnup, %		Degree of burnup, %		Degree of burnup, %	
	1 layer	5 layers	1 layer	5 layers	1 layer	5 layers
K 276	41	41	43	43	45	45
K 281	37	37	40	40	42	42
K 278	40	40	42	42	45	45
K 277	38	38	40	40	42	42
K274	48	48	-	-	-	-
K297	17	18	22	22	27	27
K282	35	35	39	39	43	43
K270	44	44	46	46	49	49
K296	24	24	29	29	34	34
K304	5	5	9	9	15	15
K293	24	24	30	30	36	36
K285	33	33	37	37	41	41
K268	47	47	-	-	-	-
K306	5	6	10	10	15	15
K302	10	11	15	15	20	20
K289	35	35	39	39	43	43
K283	40	40	43	43	46	46
K290	32	32	38	38	41	41
K273	44	44	47	47	-	-
K265	49	49	-	-	-	-
K299	17	17	22	22	28	28
K300	16	16	21	21	27	27
K272	48	48	-	-	-	-

№TVS	Campaign #1		Campaign #2		Campaign #3	
	Degree of burnup, %		Degree of burnup, %		Degree of burnup, %	
	1 layer	5 layers	1 layer	5 layers	1 layer	5 layers
K269	45	45	48	48	51	51
K286	39	39	41	41	44	44
K287	38	38	41	41	43	43
K291	35	35	38	38	41	40
K305	6	6	11	11	15	15
K301	14	14	19	19	23	23
K262	46	46	49	49	-	-
K288	39	39	42	42	45	45
K294	26	26	32	32	38	38
K303	9	9	14	14	19	19
K295	22	22	26	26	32	32
K271	43	43	45	45	48	48
K284	36	36	40	40	43	43
K298	17	17	22	22	26	26
K267	45	45	47	47	50	50
K280	38	38	40	40	42	42
K279	41	41	43	43	46	46
K292	32	32	38	38	41	40
K275	41	41	43	43	45	45
K307	-	-	5	5	10	10
K308	-	-	5	6	10	10
K309	-	-	5	5	10	10
K310	-	-	6	6	10	10
K311	-	-	-	-	5	6
K312	-	-	-	-	5	5

The degree of burnup distributions for fuel assemblies with and without control members at the end of the campaign are shown in Fig. 7.

The deviation obtained as a result of calculating the degree of burnup distribution for fuel assemblies with the average position of the rods during the reactor operation campaign from the more “accurate” one calculated for a day of reactor operation at a power of 15 MW has little effect on the results of calculating the critical states of the reactor. The difference in the calculated reactivity for the experimental critical state with different degree of burnup distribution options does not exceed 0.12% ΔK/K.

In the second task, the average degree of burnup value for the fuel assembly was calculated, taking into account all experimental positions of the control member during one campaign, and when calculating the campaign with one time step for energy production of 7500 MWh. The calculation results are presented in Table 3 and Fig. 8. It should be noted that the first step, lasting 3 days, is done to establish an equilibrium concentration of xenon-135. In this case, the average position of the control member for this period is taken, since the change in the position of the control member during this period occurs more often than allows the calculation of MCU-PTR (the time step should not

Figure 7. Axial distribution of fuel degree of burnup calculated for the average daily and average campaign positions of the control members: (a) – K287 with an initial degree of burnup of 32% without a rod; (b) – K304 with an initial degree of burnup of 0% with a rod.

Table 3. Change in the degree of burnup of IVV-2M fuel assemblies during one reactor operation campaign

Date, time	Position of the control member, cm							Fuel assembly degree of burnup, %			
	KS-1	KS-2	KS-3	KS-4	KS-5	KS-6	AR	Accurate calculation		One step in time	
								K287	K304	K287	K304
23.05.2017 00:00	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	31.96	0,00	31.96	0,00
25.05.2017 14:39	42	0	42	0	0	0	0	32.87	0.53		
27.05.2017 23:20	45	0	45	0	0	0	29	33.58	1.02		
28.05.2017 23:50	43	0	43	0	0	0	29	33.90	1.24		
29.05.2017 17:12	41	0	41	0	0	0	27	34.11	1.39		
30.05.2017 12:36	39	0	39	0	0	0	28	34,36	1.58		
31.05.2017 11:00	37	0	37	0	0	0	30	34.64	1.80		
01.06.2017 09:06	35	0	35	0	0	0	31	34.92	2.01		
02.06.2017 14:37	34	0	34	0	0	0	27	35.30	2.29		
03.06.2017 09:21	33	0	33	0	0	0	27	35.55	2.48		
04.06.2017 19:10	30	0	30	0	0	0	32	35.73	2.63		
05.06.2017 17:25	28	0	28	0	0	0	35	35.98	2.82		
07.06.2017 12:30	27	0	27	0	0	0	30	36.26	3.03		
08.06.2017 16:10	25	0	25	0	0	0	34	36.82	3.47		
10.06.2017 07:45	23	0	23	0	0	0	33	37.16	3.75		
11.06.2017 09:40	22	0	22	0	0	0	33	37.66	4.15		
14.06.2017 01:00	20	0	20	0	0	0	25	38.01	4.43	38.32	4.46

Figure 8. Change in degree of burnup in K-287 and K-304 fuel assemblies during one campaign (power generation step 7500 MW·h).

be less than 0.02 days). Information on the position of the shim rod (KS) and the automatic control (AR) is specified in the operational log of the IVV-2M RR control engineer.

Fig. 8 also presented in article (Van Thuong et al. 2023) only as a result of one of the private calculations. This paper shows the implementation of an approach to calculating the degree of burnup in fuel assemblies.

From the obtained calculation results, it is evident that the difference between the “accurate” calculation of the degree of burnup with a changing position of the control member and the calculation in one step, lasting 500 hours, is less than 1%.

Thus, the conducted studies have shown that to calculate the process of burnout of the IVV-2M RR core, it is sufficient to use a step of energy production of 7500 MWh, while the control rods should be in the average position for the campaign. A more detailed division may be necessary to calculate additional experimental critical states for program verification.

It should also be noted that the issue of the need for a single fuel element (or more detailed in the horizontal

plane) calculation of burnup degree was not considered due to the lack of control over the orientation of the IVV-2M fuel assemblies in the horizontal plane during reactor operation.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the conducted studies, it can be concluded that to calculate the degree of burnup in the IVV-2M fuel assembly with an error of no more than 1%, it is sufficient to use a cell size by the height of the active part of the fuel assembly of about 10 cm ($N_z = 5$), a calculation step for energy production of 7500 MWh, while the control members should be in the average position for the campaign. Further detailing of the degree of burnup altitude distribution has virtually no effect on the value of the multiplication factor and the calculated parameters of the “hot” spot.

The criticality of the reactor core in its various layouts serves as experimental data to confirm the calculations of burnup degree in the IVV-2M fuel assemblies.

The question of the necessity of a single fuel element (or more detailed) calculation of burnup degree is not considered in this work. This necessity may be required only if the orientation of the fuel assembly in the horizontal plane is monitored during reloads.

It should also be noted that the choice of spatial division for calculating the distribution of energy release in the IVV-2M fuel assembly, the neutron flux density in the experimental channels, ampoule devices, etc., is a separate task and was not considered in this work.

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